

Studies on 8-Substituted-10,11-Dihydro-5H Dibenzo (b, e) (1,4) Diazepin-11-Thione—Part III

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8-Amino-10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo (b,e) (1,4) diazepin-11-thione (2) was prepared by reacting 8-amino-10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo (b, e) (1,4) diazepin-11-one (1) with P_2S_5 in pyridine. 2 was converted into 8-chloro-(3), 8-iodo-(4) derivatives by Sandmeyer's reaction, 8-bromo derivative (5) by Gattermann's reaction and 8-thiol (6 and 7) derivative by reacting diazonium salt of 2 and 1 with potassium ethylxanthate. The structures of 2-7 were established on the basis of elemental analysis and IR spectral studies. Preliminary pharmacological screening of compounds 2-5 indicates that they are depressant of the central nervous system.

IN continuation of our earlier studies on dibenzodiazepines^{1,2}, which are well known CNS drugs^{3,4} the synthesis of the title compounds was carried out in order to study the comparative CNS activity of thione group at position 11-in place of carbonyl group in 1,4-dibenzodiazepine molecule having various substituents at position 8. 8-Thiol derivative (7) of (1) was also prepared on similar lines.

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|---|-----------------------|-------|
| 1 | X = NH ₂ , | Y = O |
| 2 | X = NH ₂ , | Y = S |
| 3 | X = Cl, | Y = S |
| 4 | X = I, | Y = S |
| 5 | X = Br, | Y = S |
| 6 | X = SH, | Y = S |
| 7 | X = SH, | Y = O |

8-Amino - 10,11 - dihydro - 5H-dibenzo (b,e) (1,4) diazepin-11-one was reacted with P_2S_5 in pyridine when 2-(8-amino-10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo (b, e) (1,4) diazepin-11-thione was obtained. The amino group at position-8 of 2 was reacted under Sandmeyer^{5,6} and Gattermann⁷ reaction conditions when corresponding 8-chloro (3), 8-iodo (4) and 8-bromo (5) derivatives

were obtained. The diazotised solution of 2 was reacted with potassium ethylxanthate solution when 8-thiol derivative (6) was obtained.

Experimental :

All the melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer infra-cord spectrometer in KBr pellets. Purity of compounds (2-7) were checked in Tlc using silica gel G plate and the solvent system benzene, ethanol and ammonia (7:2:1) (solvent layer) as mobile phase.

8-Amino-10,11 - Dihydro-5H - Dibenzo (b,e) (1,4) Diazepin-11-Thione (2). 1 (6.7500 g., 0.030M) was refluxed with P_2S_5 (9.300 g., 0.042 M) in dry pyridine for 4 hrs. The contents were cooled and filtered. The solvent was distilled under reduced pressure and the residue was treated with N-Na₂CO₃ soln. (90 ml). The crude product was crystallised from acetone-water (2. Rf. 0.56 ; m.p. 263° ; yield 4.68 g., 64.1% N, 17.63%). The compound showed the presence of aromatic primary amino group and sulphur.

$\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$: 3440 (m) ; 3350 (m) ; 3330 (m), 3310 (m) ; 1150(s).

8-Chloro-10,11-Dihydro - 5H - Dibenzo (b,e) (1,4) Diazepin-11-Thione (3). The diazotised solution of (2) 1.205 g., 0.005 M, in conc. HCl (3 ml), CH₃COOH (2 ml), diazotised with NaNO₂ (0.8 g) at 0-5° was added to a cold solution of Cu₂Cl₂ (0.3170 gm) dissolved in 1.5 ml of conc. HCl at 0° with continuous stirring. After stirring for 0.5 hr at 20°, the reaction mixture was finally heated over water bath till evolution of N₂

ceased (ca.1.0hr.). The contents were cooled and filtered. The crude product was crystallised from C_2H_5OH to afford the corresponding dibenzodiazepine (3, Rf. 0.69; m.p. 230°; yield 0.78 g., 60%; N, 10.98%). The compound indicated the absence of primary aromatic amino group and presence of chlorine and sulphur.

ν_{max}^{KBr} 3440 (m), 3360 (m), 1140 (s), 730 (s).

8-Iodo-10,11-Dihydro-5H-Dibenzo (b,e) (1,4) Diazepin-11-Thione (4). To the diazotised solution of 2 [(1.205 g, 0.005 M in conc. HCl (3 ml) and CH_3COOH (2 ml) diazotised with $NaNO_2$ (0.8 g)], ice cold solution of KI (1.0 g., 0.006 M) was added during 0.5 hr with stirring. The reaction mixture was warmed over water bath for 2 hr. and after basification with aq. NaOH (10%) extracted with $CHCl_3$. The $CHCl_3$ extract was washed with hypo solution and the solvent was distilled off. The crude product was crystallised from C_2H_5OH [4, Rf, 0.64; m.p. 243°; yield 0.88 g., 50%, N. 7.74%]. The compound indicated the presence of iodine and sulphur and absence of aromatic primary amino group.

ν_{max}^{KBr} 3440 (m), 3360 (m), 1135 (s), 530 (s)

8-Bromo-10,11-Dihydro-5H-Dibenzo (b,e) (1,4) Diazepin-11-Thione (5). To the diazotised solution of 2 [(1.205 g., 0.005 M in 4% HBr (3 ml) diazotised with $NaNO_2$ (0.8 g at 0-5°)], copper turning (0.20 g.) was added and the contents were heated over water bath for 4 hr. The reaction mixture, after cooling, was filtered. The crude product was crystallised from C_2H_5OH . (5) (Rf, 0.66, m.p. 160°, yield 0.95 g., 62.29%; N, 8.96%).

The compound indicated the absence of primary aromatic amino group and the presence of sulphur and bromine.

ν_{max}^{KBr} 3440 (m), 3360 (m), 1140 (s), 590 (s)

8-Thiol-10-11-Dihydro-5H-Dibenzo(b,e)(1,4)Diazepin-11-Thione (6). To the diazotised solution of 2 [(1.205 g., 0.005 M, in conc. HCl (3 ml) and CH_3COOH (2 ml), diazotised with $NaNO_2$ (0.8 g at 0-5°)] aqueous solution of potassium ethylxanthate (1.60 g, 0.01 M in 5 ml of H_2O) was added dropwise with continuous stirring at 0-5°. The stirring was continued for another 15 min at room temperature. To the well stirred contents aq. NaOH (5 cc, 10%) was added and the temperature was maintained at 0°, with stirring. The resulting complex was broken down with conc. HCl and extracted with ethylacetate. The solvent from solvent layer was distilled off to yield the crude product which was crystallised from acetone (6, Rf, 0.58; m.p. 235°; yield 0.705 g., 55%; N, 10.65%).

The compound showed the presence of sulphur and absence of aromatic primary amino group.

ν_{max}^{KBr} 3440 (m), 3360 (m), 1140 (s), 2532 (s).

On similar lines 8-thiol-10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo (b, e) (1, 4) diazepin-11-one (7) was synthesised from 1 (8-amino-10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo (b,e) (1,4) diazepin-11-one) (7 Rf, 0.54; yield, 0.629 g., 52%; N, 11.33%). The compound showed the presence of sulphur and absence of aromatic primary amino group.

ν_{max}^{KBr} 3440 (m), 3360 (m), 1660 (s), 2532 (s)

Pharmacology (Preliminary screening).

To observe the effects on the central nervous system (CNS), compounds 2-5 were injected intraperitoneally (i. p.) in mice on a body weight basis, in a gum acacia suspension. The gross effect observed was, reduction in spontaneous motor activity (SMA) and reactivity. Writhing, Straub tail phenomenon and ptosis were also observed⁸, indicating depression of the CNS.

Spontaneous Motor Activity. The method of Kinnard and Carr⁹ revealed that the compounds 2-5 significantly reduced SMA in mice.

Potentiation of pentobarbitone-induced hypnosis¹⁰
A significant potentiation of pentobarbitone sodium (50 mg/kg i.p.)-induced sleep was observed in mice on intraperitoneal administration of compounds 2-5.

From the above observations it is likely that these compounds are depressants of the CNS. Detailed studies are in progress.

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